

APPLICATION OF FITTIG'S REACTION TO THE SYNTHESIS OF SIDE-CHAIN AROMATIC ETHERS

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Bromobenzene and *para*-dibromobenzene react with chloromethyl ether in presence of metallic sodium forming benzylmethyl ether and *p*-bromobenzylmethyl ether respectively. Tribromobenzene does not react at all probably due to steric hindrance. Diphenylethyl ether is prepared which has no smell.

The chief component of the essential oil from the *Keora* perfume has been shown by Deshapande (this *Journal*, 1938, 15, 506) to be the methyl ether of β -phenylethyl alcohol (I), which has been prepared from benzylmagnesium bromide and bromomethyl ether (Hammonet, *Compt. rend.*, 1901, 138, 814) or from sodium compound of β -phenylethyl alcohol and methyl iodide or *p*-phenylethyl alcohol and methyl iodide, in presence of moist silver oxide, the alcohol itself being obtainable with difficulty.

It was therefore thought that the condensation might take place by Fittig's reaction (*Annalen*, 1864, 131, 303; 1869, 149, 334) which is generally used to build homologues of benzene; for example, bromobenzene condenses with methyl bromide in presence of metallic sodium to form toluene and bromobenzene alone gives a 5% yield of diphenyl (Fittig, *Annalen*, 1862, 121, 363; 1864, 132, 201; Ullmann, *ibid.*, 1904, 302, 40). Better results are, however, obtained with copper-bronze.

Chloromethyl ether was substituted for methyl bromide when condensation took place in presence of molecular sodium to give the methyl ether of benzyl alcohol (II). When, however, chlorobenzene was used in place of bromobenzene, the yield of (II) was poor.

Again, bromobenzene was replaced by benzyl chloride in the above reaction and it was expected that the product would be the methyl ether of β -phenylethyl alcohol (I), which seemed to have been formed in traces as could be recognised from the characteristic 'Keora' odour. But the bulk of the resulting liquid after distillation was found to contain several substances from which only dibenzyl, formed obviously by self condensation of benzyl chloride, could be obtained in the pure condition. Copper powder in place of sodium gave dibenzyl as the main product.

Hence, it seems that Fittig's reaction does not work in the production of ethers when halogen is in the side-chain and not directly linked to nucleus. But in the condensation with Grignard's reagent (Hammonet, *loc. cit.*) there is no such limitation.

In view of this, dibromobenzene was condensed with chloromethyl ether in pre-

sence of sodium wire when only the *p*-bromobenzylmethyl ether (III, b.p. 235°) was obtained and the expected demethyl ether of xylene glycol (IV), not known as far, was not formed.

The ether (III) has no fragrance like the ethers of benzyl or phenylethyl alcohols.

s-Tribromobenzene did not condense at all with chloromethyl ether in presence of sodium probably due to steric hindrance.

With a view to ascertaining whether the length of the side-chain determines in any way the smell of the ether, a long side-chain ether was synthesised by condensing sodium phenylethyl alcoholate with phenylethyl iodide when di-β-phenylethyl ether (V) was obtained. It is a solid without any smell.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chloromethyl ether was prepared in an improved yield by passing gaseous hydrochloric acid in a well cooled mixture of 33% formaldehyde and methyl alcohol (1:1.25 mols.) till saturation, when an oily layer of the ether separated, b.p. 57°-59° (cf. Henry, *Ber*, 1893, 26, 933).

Methyl Ether of Benzyl Alcohol (II).—To 6 g. (2 atoms) of molecular sodium, prepared by melting under xylene and shaking, covered with dry ether in a R.B flask a mixture of 10.5 g. of chloromethyl ether and 20 g. of bromobenzene in molecular proportion was gradually added from the top of a condenser. A vigorous reaction took place which was controlled by cooling. On keeping overnight, the precipitated sodium halides were filtered and on removal of ether the residual liquid on fractionation gave the ether (II), b. p. 165°-170°, yield 4 g. (Found: OMe, 25.6. C₈H₁₀O requires OMe, 25.4 per cent).

Condensation of chloromethyl ether with benzyl chloride in molecular proportion was attempted in presence of sodium wire in benzene solution on a water-bath. Even after refluxing for 12 hours and keeping overnight appreciable unchanged sodium remained. On working the benzene solution most of the liquid distilled between 170° and 185° which, however, was not a single substance and the temperature rose to 260° when a liquid passed over which soon solidified. It crystallised from alcohol as long prisms, m.p. 52°. This was identified to be dibenzyl. [Found: C, 92.1; H, 7.8. Calc. for (C₆H₅.CH₂)₂: C, 92.3; H, 7.7 per cent].

p-Bromobenzylmethyl Ether (III).—*p*-Dibromobenzene (18 g.), chloromethyl ether (12 g.) and sodium wire (7 g.) were made to react as in the above experiment and the resulting liquid on fractionation gave the ether (III), b. p. 130-135°, yield 8 g. (Found: C, 47.6; H, 4.9; Br, 38.9; OMe, 15.9. C₈H₈OBr requires C, 47.8; H, 4.5; Br, 39.8; OMe, 15.4 per cent).

Tribromobenzene like dibromobenzene was treated with chloromethyl ether in molecular proportion in presence of sodium wire. No reaction took place and almost whole of it was recovered unchanged.

Di-β-phenylethyl Ether (V).—Phenylethyl alcohol (10 g.) was refluxed for 5 hours with required quantity of molecular sodium in benzene. To the resulting sodium derivative phenylethyl iodide from 10 g. alcohol was added and the mixture refluxed on a water-bath for 6 hours. Benzene layer was decanted and on removing the solvent the residual liquid was distilled under reduced pressure, when a small quantity passed over at 78°-79°/4 mm., which was identified be β-phenylethyl alcohol by the formation of 3,5-dinitrobenzoate, m.p. 106° and the distillation was stopped when the residue solidified on cooling. It was crystallised from petrol ether and benzene, m.p. 52°, yield 5 g. (Found: C, 84.0; H, 8.1. $C_{16}H_{18}O$ requires C, 84.9; H, 8.1 per cent).

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Received July 8, 1950.

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Please see Jour. Ind. Chem. Socy, April, 1950, for reviews.

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